

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Constructing Antibody Validation Reports

How to construct Antibody Validation Reports (AVRs)

Authors: Elizabeth McDonough¹, Diane Saunders², Andrea J. Radtke³, Ellen M. Quardokus⁴, and Michael Caldwell⁵

Approved by: Katy Börner⁴ (May 28, 2026)

¹ GE HealthCare Technology & Innovation Center, Niskayuna, NY 12309, USA.

² Feinberg School of Medicine, Northwestern University, Chicago, IL 60611, USA.

³ Leica Microsystems Inc., 35578 Wetzlar, Germany.

⁴ Department of Intelligent Systems Engineering, Luddy School of Informatics, Computing, and Engineering, Indiana University, Bloomington, IN 47408, USA.

⁵ Biohub, Redwood City, CA 94063, USA.

Introduction

Antibody validation reports ([AVRs](#)) provide information on the characterization of individual antibodies for multiplexed antibody-based imaging assays. AVRs additionally report details not included by antibody vendors such as the best performing conjugate for a particular clone and/or the impact of cycle order on immunogenicity. The current AVR database, and AVR Search website, allows validated antibodies to be filtered by Clonality, Conjugate, Host, Method, and Organ. AVR metadata is uploaded via a CEDAR templated input form. AVR details are provided as a text file and saved as a PDF for submission to the AVR upload site. AVR queries can be downloaded as a CSV file and individual AVRs can be viewed or downloaded as a PDF file.

AVRs are tightly integrated with [Organ Mapping Antibody Panels](#) (OMAPs) used in the Human Reference Atlas. Each OMAP lists a comprehensive panel of curated antibodies that identifies major anatomical structures and cell types present in a specific organ. The selected antibodies are optimized for a tissue preservation method and multiplexed imaging modality. Both efforts share standardized metadata fields that will facilitate construction of a searchable antibody database and the HRA knowledge graph.

The primary audience for this SOP includes experts authoring, validating, or publishing AVRs. This SOP assumes basic working knowledge of highly multiplexed antibody-based imaging (Hickey et al. 2022; Quardokus et al. 2023) and the HRA effort (Börner et al. 2025, 2021).

Roles and responsibilities for those with a part in the procedures are listed in **Table 1**. Resources such as templates, spreadsheets, GitHub repositories, and other materials that are used to implement the procedures are listed in **Table 2**.

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Roles and Responsibilities

AVR Author(s) are subject matter experts with backgrounds in antibody characterization and validation, histology, and/or multiplexed antibody-based imaging techniques.

AVR Reviewers are subject matter experts in antibody characterization and validation, histology, and/or multiplexed antibody-based imaging techniques.

The **Lead ASCT+B Integration Contact** is a person who works with the Lead AVR and Lead OMAP Contacts to facilitate connections between AVRs, OMAPs, and the [ASCT+B Reporter](#). This person coordinates communication between ASCT+B and Affinity Reagent Working Groups (ARWG).

The **Lead AVR Assembly Contact** is responsible for communicating with AVR authors and reviewers.

The **Lead AVR Database Liaison** is the (ARWG) Technical Project Manager who communicates the agenda for monthly meetings and facilitates the integration of AVRs and OMAPs. This person also communicates directly with the development team(s) responsible for developing and maintaining the searchable AVR database.

The **Lead AVR Quality Control Contact** is responsible for reviewing AVRs for completion and metadata standardization with AVR reviewers.

The **Lead OMAP Contact** is responsible for coordinating AVR deliverables by OMAP Authors.

Table 1. Roles, names, and email addresses of key personnel.

Role	Name	Email
AVR Author(s)	Various, depends on AVR	
AVR Reviewers	Elizabeth McDonough Andrea Radtke Diane Saunders Christophe Werlein Anna Martinez Casals Presha Rajbhandari	elizabeth.mcdonough@gehealthcare.com andrea.radtke@leica-microsystems.com diane.saunders@northwestern.edu Werlein.Christopher@mh-hannover.de anna.martinez@scilifelab.se pr2162@columbia.edu
Lead ASCT+B Integration Contact	Ellen M. Quardokus	ellenmq@iu.edu
Lead AVR Assembly Contact	Elizabeth McDonough	elizabeth.mcdonough@gehealthcare.com
Lead AVR Database Liaison	vacant	vacant
Lead AVR Quality Control Contact	Diane Saunders	diane.saunders@northwestern.edu
Lead OMAP Contact	Andrea J. Radtke	andrea.radtke@leica-microsystems.com

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Relevant Resources

Table 2. Websites, tools, and files required for AVR editing and usage. Abbreviations used in Lead column: HRA=HRA team, JCS=University of Pittsburgh team, ARWG=Lead AVR Assembly Contact (see Table 1).

Name	Purpose	Link	Lead
OMAP website	Search, filter, download OMAPs.	https://humanatlas.io/omap	HRA
AVR website	Search, filter, download AVRs.	https://avr.xconsortia.org	JCS
Information on the Affinity Reagent Imaging and Validation Working Group	This working group defines best practices for antibody use across consortia.	https://hubmapconsortium.org/open-working-groups	JCS
AVR Upload	Allows new reports to be uploaded to the HuBMAP AVR tracking system and links to documentation, including a template tsv file.	https://avr.xconsortia.org/upload	JCS
AVR Validator	Allows validation of AVR TSV file.	https://metadatavalidator.mediatacenter.org	JCS
AVR FAQ	Answers to frequently asked questions.	https://docs.hubmapconsortium.org/avr/avr-faq.html	ARWG
AVR document template	Blank template for the AVR report.	https://software.docs.hubmapconsortium.org/avr/avr-template-form-v2.docx	ARWG
AVR example as PDF	Example AVR demonstrating information to be included.	https://software.docs.hubmapconsortium.org/avr/example-avr-v2.pdf	ARWG
AVR TSV template	Blank template for the header/metadata information that must be included with each AVR document.	https://software.docs.hubmapconsortium.org/avr/avr-template-v2.csv	ARWG
AVR TSV Structure documentation	Provides definitions of the columns required in the AVR TSV file.	https://docs.hubmapconsortium.org/avr/tsv-format-v2.html	ARWG
AVR TSV example	Example of a completed TSV file that passes validation.	https://docs.hubmapconsortium.org/avr/example-avrs-v2.tsv	ARWG

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OMAP TSV template	Given many shared fields, authors of OMAPs can use a completed OMAP table as a starting point to facilitate completion of the AVR TSV template.	https://hubmapconsortium.github.io/ccf/pages/omap-extras/omap-table-template.xlsx	ARWG
AVR Directory	Upload final AVR files for publication.	https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1khJmkAcPwmH0whaL08uyaYh-WNM6KYZ9	ARWG

Procedures

Given an OMAP (Hickey et al. 2022; Quardokus et al. 2023) with, e.g., 50 antibodies (i.e., 50 AVRs), compile 50 rows in the AVR TSV file and 50 separate DOC files to be uploaded as PDF files.

As many fields are shared across OMAPs and AVRs, authors of OMAPs can use a completed OMAP table as a starting point to facilitate completion of the AVR TSV template. AVRs can be uploaded singly or in batches.

Review existing AVRs for your tissue and preservation method to see good examples and reuse existing AVRs whenever possible to avoid duplication.

Review existing AVRs

- Go to the [AVR website](#) and search, filter, or download existing AVRs.
- Access information about the Affinity Reagents Working Group (ARWG), Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs), HuBMAP AVRs including Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs), and upload new AVRs (Add AVRs in top right menu).

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1014 results found in 9ms

Target Symbol	UniProt#	Clonality	Method	Tissue Preservation	Validation Report	OMAP ID	HuBMAP ID	Previous Revision ID
MS4A1	P11836	monoclonal	IBEX	1% PFA fixed frozen	CD20_OMAP1.pdf	OMAP-1	HBM282.JNHP.445	
SPARC	P09486	polyclonal	IBEX	1% PFA fixed frozen	SPARC_OMAP1.pdf	OMAP-1	HBM787.JWBW.429	
GCG	P01275	monoclonal	CODEX	FFPE	proGlucagon-CODEX-OMAP6.pdf	OMAP-6	HBM934.WBFB.853	
FOXP3	Q9BZS1	monoclonal	IBEX	1% PFA fixed frozen	FOXP3_OMAP1.pdf	OMAP-1	HBM532.TBCC.248	
CD209	Q9NNX6	monoclonal	IBEX	1% PFA fixed frozen	DC-SIGN_OMAP1.pdf	OMAP-1	HBM736.RPSC.469	

Figure 1. Screenshot of the AVR website.

AVR TSV and DOC construction

- To upload a new AVR, two files are needed: one or more AVR document files and an AVR TSV file. Each row in the TSV file should correspond to a single AVR, allowing multiple AVRs to be uploaded in a single submission.
- **Table 2** provides links to templates and examples for AVR TSV and DOC files. Download relevant files and fill in the required information as outlined in **Table 3** and **Table 4**. Optional Fields and instruction section below.
- All AVR authors should provide their ORCID IDs. To get an ORCID ID, please visit <https://orcid.org>.

AVR TSV validation

- The TSV file must be uploaded to the [Metadata Spreadsheet Validator](#) to validate the metadata records prior to uploading.
- When your AVR document file(s) and AVR TSV file are ready for review, please notify the Lead AVR Assembly Contact by email. See **Table 1** for roles, names, and email addresses of key personnel.

AVR guidelines

AVRs provide details on controls used for characterization (positive and negative tissues for the protein of interest, cell lines, isotype controls, etc.), exemplar imaging data, and information on other antibodies tested. AVR characterization data is specific to multiplexed imaging and goes

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beyond the information typically provided by the manufacturer, including considerations such as direct conjugation and cycling effects.

While some fields in the AVR template are optional or supplemental, we ask that you share as much information as you can.

Authors are strongly encouraged to evaluate cellular location, spatial pattern, and colocalization with orthogonal markers in positive and negative control tissues. Resources for evaluating the cellular location and tissue distribution of protein biomarkers can be found in Hickey's *Nature Methods* Perspective (Hickey et al. 2022), [Table S2](#), and in the following online resources:

- [The Human Protein Atlas](#)
- [Uniprot](#)
- [GeneCards](#)

Qualitative assessment criteria include, but are not limited to, the following three properties:

- Specificity:
 - Expected staining patterns are observed based on positive and negative controls, colocalization with orthogonal markers, vendor data sheets, and descriptions from the literature.
 - Non-specific binding and/or fluorescent artifacts are minimized and assessed against true signal from positive controls.
- Sensitivity
 - Antibody titration should be performed to optimize signal-to-noise ratios and yield optimal dynamic range for a biomarker of interest.
 - Potential evaluation of different antibody formats to identify antibodies that provide the best performance.
- Reproducibility
 - The antibody's performance should be consistent across multiple experiments and internal users.
 - In the case of polyclonal antibodies, authors have confirmed minimal lot-to-lot variability.
 - Recombinant and knock-out antibodies should be prioritized for further reproducibility and continuous access.

Standardized AVR metadata fields

The following tables provide definitions and guidelines for filling out target and antibody information in the standardized format. This information will be entered into both the AVR document and AVR TSV files.

Table 3. Metadata schema for required fields in AVR files.

Field name in AVR	Description	Required Format	Examples
Target name (target_name)	This is the name of the protein that the antibody is targeting.	Commonly used name or protein abbreviation	CD20, ICAM, Somatostatin

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Field name in AVR	Description	Required Format	Examples
	Please list the UniProt protein name. This may be different from the common name for the protein.		
HGNC_ID	Gene identification number from Human Gene Ontology Nomenclature Committee (HGNC) encoding the target protein.	HGNC:####	HGNC:4947, HGNC:3612
UniProt accession number (uniprot_accession_number)	Identifies the target protein (see UniProt). For human protein panels, be certain to include human protein designation. If UniProt ID cannot be found for the antibody, please leave the field blank.	Alphanumeric (see https://www.uniprot.org/help/accession_numbers) ; for multiclonal (pan-) antibodies, list IDs for all targeted proteins separated by commas.	A2BC19, P12345, Q9BZS1
RRID (rrid)	Allows for universal identification of an antibody (search by catalog number at https://scicrunch.org/resources) . If there is no entry, please register your antibody.	AB_#####	AB_793620, AB_10124480
Host species (host)	Identifies the species in which the antibody was raised.	Capitalize first letter.	Rabbit, Donkey, Mouse
Antibody isotype (isotype)	Describes the antibody isotype.	Please write out any symbols.	IgG, IgG1, IgG1 kappa
Clonality (clonality)	Identifies whether the antibody targets a single epitope (monoclonal) or a heterogeneous mix recognizing multiple epitopes on the same antigen (polyclonal).	Monoclonal or Polyclonal.	Monoclonal, Polyclonal
Clone ID clone_id	Provides the unique identifier for a laboratory-generated antibody produced either by hybridoma cells or through recombinant DNA technology.	List clone as provided by the manufacturer. If polyclonal, leave this field blank.	1A4, L26, EPR5386
Antibody vendor (vendor)	This is the company that sells the antibody.	Vendor name	Cell Signaling Technology, Abcam, BioLegend

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Field name in AVR	Description	Required Format	Examples
Antibody catalog number (catalog_number)	Provides catalog number from vendor for the source of the antibody.	Vendor catalog number	Ab9566, sc-20060, C6198
Recombinant (recombinant)	Classifies the antibody as recombinant or not. Recombinant antibodies (rAbs) are monoclonal antibodies which are generated in vitro using synthetic genes.	Indicate Y for yes, N for no.	Y, N
Tissue Preservation Technique (tissue_preservation)	Preservation technique used. If fixative other than formalin, indicate the percentage of fixative indicated (e.g., 1% or 4%).	Use a common abbreviation format (e.g., FFPE for formalin fixed paraffin embedded).	FFPE, Fresh frozen 1% PFA fixed frozen
Organ or tissue used (organ)	Organ or tissue used for initial antibody validation and characterization. For OMAPs, this field may report the organ for which the OMAP is designated.	Commonly used anatomical name.	Urinary bladder, Pancreas
Organ or tissue ontology ID (organ_uberont)	Ontology identifier for the organ or tissue (organ in row above).	Please use common ontology if possible (e.g., Uberon).	UBERON:0002113, FMA:7198
Antibody-based imaging method (method)	Specific antibody-based imaging technique (can be multiplexed).	Provide standard abbreviation of method.	CODEX, IBEX, Cell DIVE, SIMS
Conjugate (conjugate)	Specifies addition to the antibody (e.g., fluorophore, heavy metal, oligonucleotide) enabling detection, if applicable. If no conjugate, leave blank.	For fluorophores, please use industry standard abbreviations (e.g., AF for Alexa Fluorophore™). Capitalize the first letter.	AF647, PE, Oligonucleotide, 146Nd, Atto550
Author ORCID	Identifies the individual who validated the antibody used in the assay.	####-####-####-#### (the last digit may be X)	https://info.orcid.org/researchers
Vendor affiliation	Identifies whether the antibody validation was done by a commercial entity (antibody vendor or multiplexed technology provider).	Vendor name. If not applicable, please leave this field blank.	Cell Signaling Technology, Bio-Techne, Abcam, Biolegend, Akoya Biosciences, Leica Microsystems

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Table 4. Metadata Schema for optional fields in AVR files.

Field name in AVR	Description	Required Format	Examples
OMAP ID	Unique identifier assigned to OMAP at time of publication.	OMAP with number based on date created.	OMAP-1, OMAP-2
Lot number of validated antibody (lot_number)	Allows for monitoring of lot-to-lot variation.	Number listed on antibody vial. If lot numbers are not available, please leave this field blank.	B256112, 16A5T1, KPY01191
Antigen retrieval details (antigen_retrieval)	If applicable, indicate general conditions under which antigen retrieval was performed. Additional details should be available in the referenced protocol (see protocol_doi field).	pH values; if multiple, separate by commas	6 9 6,9
Manuscript citation DOI (manuscript_doi)	Provides citation of this antibody's characterization or use.	https://doi.org/... or https://dx.doi.org/...	https://dx.doi.org/10.1101/2022.03.30.486438
Validation protocol DOI (protocol_doi)	Details the protocol used to validate the antibody, including positive and negative controls and example images. To enhance reproducibility, we recommend that all protocols be made publicly available via protocols.io or another open protocol repository.	https://doi.org/... or https://dx.doi.org/...	https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.bqjimuke
concentration_value in µg/mL	Provides a recommended usage in standardized units (µg/mL). If providing dilution instead, leave this field blank.	Numeric only (units standardized).	5, 2.6, 0.554
dilution	Provides a recommended dilution factor. If providing a concentration instead, leave this field blank.	1:#### (please use colon and not a slash or backslash)	1:100, 1:50, 1:2000
cycle_number	Identifies the cycle number in which an antibody was either applied to the tissue or, in the case of CODEX, visualized with a fluorescent reporter. For non-cyclic methods use 1 for all cycles.	Numeric	6, 1, 14
fluorescent_reporter	For indirect visualization (e.g., oligo-conjugated antibodies), define the fluorescent reporter	Fluorophore only. Please use industry	AF488, Cy3, Atto550

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Field name in AVR	Description	Required Format	Examples
	utilized in the corresponding cycle. For metal or fluorophore-conjugated antibodies, please leave blank.	standard abbreviations (e.g., AF for Alexa Fluorophore™).	

Instructions for completing the AVR document file

To fill out the AVR document file, first enter the standardized metadata into sections I (Target Information) and II (Antibody Information). Descriptions and examples of these fields are provided in **Table 3** and **Table 4**. If you do not provide information for optional fields, please leave them blank.

Exemplary Image: We ask that you provide an exemplary image of the antibody stain from a representative dataset. Please include an image that highlights expected localization and/or subcellular colocalization with a marker that stains the same cell type or organelle, i.e., pseudo colored image with DAPI overlay for a nuclear marker, colocalization with a marker that stains the same subcellular compartment or cell type, etc. Please include a scale bar and provide appropriate magnification to see detail. Please share JPG, TIF, or PNG images at 300 ppi.

Validation Data: This section includes both vendor and laboratory validation information. Please see Section on AVR Guidelines for descriptions of major assessment pillars (specificity, sensitivity, and reproducibility). Please keep in mind that if multiple antibodies from different vendors are compared, the same display threshold should be applied to the comparable fields of view in serial sections and similar regions/features of the tissue. Images obtained from control samples should be assessed simultaneously to aid assessment of specificity; please include side-by-side comparisons in your AVR whenever possible.

Vendor validation (**Table 5**) captures the datasheet reference, access date, and recommended applications. Laboratory validation (**Table 6**) documents the controls used to assess antibody performance, including positive and negative tissues, isotype controls, peptide blocking, phosphatase treatment, and cell line models, with space to specify relevant tissues and additional controls. **Table 7** provides a record of other antibodies evaluated for the same target, including vendor and catalog information, clonality, and whether each antibody is considered a suitable backup or not recommended, with justification where applicable.

Table 5. Vendor validation.

Data sheet URL	Please link to URL of vendor datasheet
Date accessed	Please provide the date when the datasheet was accessed in MM/DD/YY format.
Vendor suggested use	SDS-PAGE, WB, IHC, IF, etc.

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Table 6. Laboratory validation. Controls used: Place an “X” below controls that apply, and provide details where available.

Positive/negative control tissues	Isotype control	Peptide block	Phosphatase treatment	Cell line controls	Other (please list)
Please list tissues					

Table 7. Other antibodies tested. Enter information for other antibodies tested for this target. Add rows as necessary.

Vendor and catalog number	Clonality	Backup clone or not recommended
		If not recommended, provide reason if possible (sensitivity, could not conjugate, etc).

Supplemental Data: This section of the AVR is optional but highly encouraged. We ask that you provide data that highlights initial screening of the antibody, cyclic effects, conjugation success, etc. An example of how to do this can be [found here](#).

Export/save your Document file as a PDF and title it as [target_name-method]. This file name will be entered into the final column of the AVR TSV.

Instructions for completing the AVR TSV

Using the TSV file sample in **Table 2**, enter information for one antibody per row, using the fields in **Tables 3-4**. In the last column (avr_filename), please enter the associated AVR document file name (saved as a PDF).

Please note that the AVR TSV template was developed from the OMAP Table template (**Table 2**) (Quardokus et al. 2023) in order to facilitate easy AVR submission by OMAP authors. If you are submitting AVRs only (not part of an OMAP), you can leave the following fields blank:

- cycle_number
- fluorescent_reporter

Instructions for submitting AVRs if you are a HuBMAP member

- Go to the AVR Website and click on Add AVRs in the upper right corner, as shown in **Fig. 1**.
- For security purposes, you will be taken to a Globus login page.
- Once logged in, there are several links to resources, templates and examples of filled in reports.

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Antibody Validation Report Upload

Antibody Validation Report

The HuBMAP Antibody Validation Report Upload allows new reports to be uploaded to the HuBMAP AVR tracking system.

To upload a report, follow the steps outlined in the [Uploading new reports](#) documentation. You will need to create a .tsv file according to the [TSV Structure](#) documentation. We have also provided a [template tsv file](#) to get you started.

Antibody Files

Upload a single tsv file describing the AVRs being uploaded (see [Uploading new reports](#) and [TSV Structure](#)).

No file chosen

Antibody PDFs

Upload the PDF files associated with the tsv by clicking Browse. To easily upload place all files in a single directory and use the ctrl (or command on Mac) key to select them all in the file dialog.

No file chosen

Figure 2. Screenshot of the page for the AVR Validation Report Upload.

Instructions for submitting AVRs if you are not a HuBMAP member

1. Uploading requires two documents, the completed AVR PDF file(s) and the completed AVR TSV file containing metadata and AVR PDF file names.
2. Please contact the Lead AVR Assembly Contact (**Table 1**) for details on how to contribute your AVRs.

References and Resources

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Glossary

antibody reproducibility: Consistent performance of an antibody across lots or batches.

antibody sensitivity: The ability of an antibody to detect target antigens of varying abundance. This can be influenced by assay specific factors such as the formulation and concentration of the antigen, antigen retrieval, temperature, and time.

antibody specificity: The ability of an antibody to recognize and bind to its intended epitope and not bind to other off-target epitopes. This can be determined with appropriate positive and negative controls.

antibody validation report (AVR): Document providing details on the characterization of individual antibodies for multiplexed antibody-based imaging assays. These details include target protein information (e.g., target name, UniProt accession number), and antibody

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information (e.g., RRID, host organism, vendor, catalog number, lot number). AVRs also provide details on controls used for antibody characterization and validation (positive and negative tissues, cell lines, isotype controls, etc), exemplar imaging data, and information on other antibodies tested.

AVR TSV: The spreadsheet (TSV file format) submitted with AVR document(s) that enables antibody metadata to be incorporated into the HuBMAP AVR database (HuBMAP AVR search). One AVR TSV file can contain metadata information for several AVRs, since the AVR document file name is one of the metadata fields.

AVR document: The AVR document (saved as a PDF) completed by the AVR author that provides detailed information on antibody characterization. One AVR document is submitted per protein target.

Cell DIVE: The Cell DIVE multiplexed imaging solution is an integrated system for imaging 60+ biomarkers from one tissue sample at the single-cell level. The tissue-preserving staining and dye inactivation workflow and advanced image processing enables a more comprehensive understanding of the tissue microenvironment than has been available with traditional chromogenic- or fluorescence-based imaging (Gerdes et al. 2013).

CO-Detection by indEXing (CODEX): see **PhenoCycler**

comma-separated values (CSV): This is a text file that has a specific format which allows data to be saved in a table structure.

conjugate: Fluorescent dye, oligonucleotide, metal or enzyme covalently attached to a primary or secondary antibody that is used for downstream detection of the antibody bound to its target in/on a cell.

fixed frozen: Method of tissue preservation where samples are placed in fixative (e.g., formalin), cryoprotected with sucrose, frozen in molds with optimal cutting temperature (OCT) media, and stored at -80C.

formalin fixed paraffin embedded (FFPE): Most common form of tissue preservation where tissues have undergone chemical fixation by saturating them with formalin followed by embedding in paraffin wax to enhance preservation and facilitate sectioning of the tissue. Samples are stored at room temperature.

fresh frozen (FF): Method of tissue preservation where samples are frozen at ultralow temperature without fixative (fresh), immobilized in cryosafe media (e.g., OCT, carboxymethyl cellulose), and stored at -80C.

imaging mass cytometry (IMC): Multiplexed imaging method that employs metal-conjugated antibodies applied in a single master mix to tissues. Target-specific antibodies are detected using laser ablation coupled to mass cytometry (Giesen et al. 2014).

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immunohistochemistry (IHC): Laboratory technique used to visualize proteins in cells or tissues using specific primary antibodies conjugated to chromogens.

Immunostaining with Signal Amplification by Exchange Reaction (Immuno-SABER): A highly multiplexed and signal amplification method free of in situ enzymatic reactions that utilizes oligonucleotide-conjugated antibodies and complementary fluorescent imagers (Saka et al. 2019).

Iterative Bleaching Extends Multiplexity (IBEX): An open source iterative immunolabeling and chemical bleaching method for high-content imaging of diverse tissues (Radtke, Chu, et al. 2022; Radtke et al. 2020).

iterative indirect immunofluorescence imaging (4i): A cyclic high-content imaging method for visualizing cellular and subcellular structures in situ (Gut et al. 2018).

MACSima Imaging Cyclic Staining (MICS): Immunofluorescent imaging method for hundreds of protein targets across a single specimen at subcellular resolution based on cycles of staining, imaging, and erasure. This method uses photobleaching of fluorescent labels of recombinant antibodies (REAffinity Antibodies) or release of antibodies (REAlase Antibodies) or their labels (REAdye_release Antibodies). The commercial platform (MACSima Imaging System) is a fully automated instrument based on fluorescence microscopy, recombinant ready-to-use antibody-fluorochrome conjugates, sample carriers and a MACS iQ View Analysis Software for data analysis (Kinkhabwala et al. 2022; Schäfer et al. 2021).

multiplexed ion beam imaging (MIBI): Multiplexed imaging method that employs metal-conjugated antibodies applied in a single master mix to tissues and an ion beam for tag ionization (Angelo et al. 2014; Lomeli et al. 2021).

Open Researcher and Contributor ID (ORCID): Unique identifier number researchers own and control that connects the ID with professional information—affiliations, grants, publications, etc. and can be used during the publication process. See <https://orcid.org>.

Organ Mapping Antibody Panel (OMAP): A comprehensive panel of curated antibodies that identifies the major anatomical structures and cell types in a specific organ. The selected antibodies are optimized for a tissue preservation method (i.e., fixed, frozen) and multiplexed imaging modality (e.g., CODEX, Cell DIVE) through published protocols (protocols.io) and AVR.

PhenoCycler: This multiparameter imaging method, formerly known as CO-Detection by indEXing (CODEX), relies on oligonucleotide-conjugated antibodies and the cyclic addition and removal of complementary fluorescently labeled oligonucleotide probes. The commercial fluidics and high-plex image acquisition platform (Akoya Biosciences, Marlborough, MA) for this method enables whole slide imaging of up to 100 biomarkers on tissue samples in situ (Black et al. 2021; Goltsev et al. 2018; Kennedy-Darling et al. 2021).

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polyclonal antibody: A mixture of antibodies derived from distinct B-lymphocyte populations that detect multiple epitopes within the same immunogen. Production of polyclonal antibodies typically involves the collection of blood from the immunized animal, isolation of the immunoglobulin fraction, and affinity purification to remove non-specific antibody populations. These antibodies can be used for research purposes to detect the corresponding antigen in or on cells in a tissue. An antibody binds to an antigen or protein target directly. Primary antibodies are most often conjugated covalently to a fluorescent dye, oligonucleotide, metal or enzyme for downstream detection methods. Note that polyclonal antibodies can exhibit significant lot-to-lot variability, which can impact their performance in experiments. This variability arises from differences in immunization protocols, host animals, and conditions during production.

primary antibody: An immunoglobulin made in response to a specific antigen (often a protein) that causes an immune response in an animal. These antibodies can be used for research purposes to detect the corresponding antigen in or on cells in a tissue. An antibody binds to an antigen or protein target directly. Primary antibodies are most often conjugated covalently to a fluorescent dye, oligonucleotide, metal or enzyme for downstream detection methods.

Research Resource Identifiers (RRIDs): Unique identifiers for referencing a biomedical reagent or resource. See <https://www.rrids.org>.

secondary antibody: An antibody that is used to indirectly visualize a primary antibody. Secondary antibodies are made by immunizing a host animal with antibodies of a different species (e.g., goat anti-rabbit secondary antibodies derived from goat immunized with rabbit IgG) and are used to detect species- and isotype-specific primary antibodies (e.g., goat anti-rabbit IgG paired with primary antibody made in rabbit). Secondary antibodies are most often conjugated covalently to a fluorescent dye, oligonucleotide, metal or enzyme for downstream detection methods and are sometimes used to amplify the signal of the antigen-bound primary antibody.

secondary ion mass spectrometry (SIMS): A technique capable of imaging tissues, single cells, and microbes revealing chemical species with sub-micrometer spatial resolution (Anderton and Gamble 2016). SIMS is used as a multiplexed imaging method by detecting metal-conjugated antibodies where an ion beam generates ejected ions detected with a mass spectrometer.

tissue-based cyclic immunofluorescence (t-CyCIF): A cyclic high-content imaging method employing commercial antibodies and diverse microscope configurations, based on the approach of chemically inactivating fluorophores after iterative rounds of immunofluorescence (Lin et al. 2015, 2018; Black et al. 2021). See <https://www.cycif.org>.

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